

1 Response to Comment on 'Valid 2 Molecular Dynamics Simulations of 3 Human Hemoglobin Require a 4 Surprisingly Large Box Size'

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12
13 **Abstract** The Comment does not provide convincing evidence that the conclusions of
14 the original article are incorrect. Specifically, the studies do not invalidate the conclusion
15 that there is a significant box size dependence of the stability of the unliganded T state in
16 hemoglobin. Moreover, there are numerous statements in the Comment that require
17 clarification by further investigations.

19 Introduction

20 Our investigation of the box size dependence of hemoglobin in solution was initiated
21 by the disagreement between the experimentally observed *Edelstein (1971)* stabilization
22 of the unliganded T state (T(0)) relative to an R-like structure and several publications
23 using molecular dynamics simulations *Hub et al. (2010)*; *Yusuff et al. (2012)* which found
24 that the T(0) state was not stable and made a transition to an R-like state in times on the
25 order of a hundred nanoseconds. We began research to determine what could be wrong
26 with the published simulations and found, after looking at many possibilities *El Hage et al.*
27 *(2018)* that only a surprisingly large (150 Å) simulation box was able to stabilize the T(0)
28 state over at least ~ 1.3 microseconds, see Figure 1.

30 Results

31 *Statistics:* To estimate rates, a sufficient number of samples is required. An explicit exam-
32 ple, although not related to hemoglobin but illustrating the effect of insufficient statistics,
33 is to consider reactive MD simulations for the vibrationally induced photodissociation

Figure 1. Temporal change of the $C\alpha$ - $C\alpha$ distance between His₁₄₆B2 and His₁₄₆B2 for the 150 Å box during 1280 ns of MD.

34 of HSO₃Cl to SO₃ and HCl, see Figure 2. It is evident that with 20 events the distribution
 35 of reaction times is far from converged and does not even allow one to guess the true
 36 distribution. For details on the simulations, see Ref. *Yosa Reyes et al. (2016)*. This is also
 37 why from *ab initio* MD simulations of vibrationally induced photodissociation *Miller and*
 38 *Gerber (2006)* no rates were determined because widely different reaction times for indi-
 39 vidual trajectories were found, as shown in their Figure 2, when only considering ~ 100
 40 trajectories.

41
 42 It also remains unclear in the Comment how the probability of 0.0026 was determined.

43
 44 *Hydrophobic Effect:* As stated in the abstract of the original article, *El Hage et al. (2018)* "The
 45 results suggest that such a large box is required for the hydrophobic effect, which stabi-
 46 lizes the T(0) tetramer, to be manifested." We felt we did not have conclusive evidence for
 47 the role of the hydrophobic effect, and have been working with Adam Willard to investi-
 48 gate this point. We note that on page 3 of the Comment, there is a list of some differences
 49 in the simulation setups. These and some additional differences in the two sets of setups
 50 need to be investigated as possible contributors to the difference in the simulation re-
 51 sults; see also below. A possible problem with the comparisons in their Figure 3 concerns
 52 the fact that we only exchanged input files for the 90 Å box and the larger boxes were
 53 constructed by them. In that regard, it is interesting to note that their observed life time
 54 for the 90 Å box with its error bars essentially includes the one observed in our simulation.

55
 56 However, we do not agree with the constructs used in the Comment to reanalyze our
 57 results. These include:

- 58 • The subvolume analysis which attempts to compare the diffusivity in large boxes
 59 but restricted to a smaller subvolume needs to introduce "imaginary boundary
 60 conditions" and it is still unclear how this was done. Such an approach appears
 61 to assume that water outside this artificial volume behaves as bulk water which is
 62 not evident and the reply to our query is unsatisfactory. Alternatively, very short

Figure 2. Reaction time distribution $p(\tau)$ for the decomposition $\text{HSO}_3\text{Cl} \rightarrow \text{SO}_3 + \text{HCl}$ from 20 (black), 500 (red) and 5000 (blue) reactive trajectories. With 20 trajectories the distribution is far from converged and even with 500 trajectories convergence appears to be incomplete. Only for 5000 independent events $p(\tau)$ approaches a smooth distribution.

- 63 analysis times (~ 2 ps) need to be used to avoid significant displacement of the
 64 water molecules. *Persson et al. (2017)*
- 65 • The water-water hydrogen bond network reconfigures when the structure of the
 66 protein changes (T vs. R) and from one box size to another box size, see Figure
 67 3 in Ref. *El Hage et al. (2018)*. Following a transition in the protein structure these
 68 changes occur on the few nanosecond time scale, as a direct response to the protein
 69 structure change. This suggests that the protein and water dynamics are coupled
 70 and can not be viewed independently.
 - 71 • As an important test we have solvated the decayed (i.e. R-state) structure from the
 72 simulation in the 120 Å box in the 150 Å box and observed that the T-state is partially
 73 recovered, see Figure 3. Apparently, solvation of the decayed structure in the larger
 74 water box provides the driving force required to partially recover the T(0) structure.
 75 This is an additional indication that thermodynamically, T(0) is favoured over R(0)
 76 in the largest water box without, however, providing information concerning a
 77 quantitative measure of the underlying energetics. Full recovery would require
 78 much longer simulations.
 - 79 • Technically, it is desirable to carry out simulations in a setup that allows the solvent
 80 - here water - to behave as a pure liquid for quantities such as $g(r)$ or the average
 81 number of H-bonds. With Hb as the solute we find this to be the case for a box size

82 of 150 Å.

Figure 3. Temporal change in the 150 Å box of (from top to bottom) the $C\alpha$ - $C\alpha$ distance between His₁₄₆B1 and His₁₄₆B2 $C\alpha$ - $C\alpha$ distance between His₁₄₃B1 and His₁₄₃B2, and the $C\alpha$ RMSD relative to the 2DN2 X-ray structure. The green and red lines report the time series reported in our article (simulation starting from the T(0) state) and the time series of a simulation starting from the decayed T(0) state (i.e. an R(0)-state structure) from R state in the 120 Å box, respectively. Cyan and blue arrows indicate the values of the corresponding observables found for the deoxy T(0) (2DN2) and oxy R(4) (2DN3) states, respectively.

83 The normalization procedure of the radial distribution functions used in the Comment
 84 remains unclear. It should be noted that the radial distribution functions in Ref. *El Hage*
 85 *et al. (2018)* follow the expectations for spherical cavities. *Chandler (2005)* Figure 5 in the
 86 original manuscript aims at highlighting that in a box not sufficiently large water barely
 87 reaches bulk properties as judged from the $g(r)$ whereas using a sufficiently large box (e.g.
 88 150 Å) readily does so. As no hydrophobic effect is expected for ubiquitin it also remains
 89 unclear what the data in Figure 2-supplement 1 contribute to relating the thermodynamic
 90 stability of the T(0) state of Hb with the hydrophobic effect.

91

92 *Kinetics as a function of box size:* This section raises questions as to the statistical sig-
 93 nificance of the results. As mentioned above and in Figure 2, converged reaction time

94 distributions require hundreds to thousands of transitions. Given the fact that the T(0)-
95 state is unstable in the 90 Å and 120 Å boxes it is reasonable that starting from an
96 ensemble of initial structures a distribution of decay times is found. Comparing two such
97 distributions to provide evidence for the presence or absence of a box size dependence
98 requires them to be converged to some degree which probably can not be achieved from
99 10 to 20 simulations.

100

101 On page 3, it is stated that with the setup used in our simulations 20 simulations were
102 done for 90 Å and 150 Å boxes and 10 for a 120 Å box. Their Figure 3 plots the results
103 which do show a box size dependence, but it is the inverse of what might be expected;
104 the transition as determined by them is shorter in the larger boxes. This surprising result
105 could be due to poor statistics, to some inconsistency in the use of our setup (see above),
106 or to something we do not understand. Interestingly, the T(0)-lifetime in the 90 Å box, for
107 which we had made input files available, is in the range we found (see Figure 1B in *El Hage*
108 *et al. (2018)*) whereas this is not the case for the 120 Å and 150 Å boxes for which no input
109 files had been sent by us. We also note a difference in the magnitude of the error bars in
110 Figure 3A for the different protonation states which requires an explanation. Additional
111 exchanges of information and detailed analyses would serve to clarify these points.

112

113 When we were still collaborating to investigate the origin of some of the results reported
114 in the Comment, we exchanged input files they used in their work and our input files. The
115 Hub paper *Hub et al. (2010)* does not provide details on the protonation states of the His,
116 except for His146 for which they used either doubly protonated or protonation at ϵ . In
117 Vesper and De Groot 2013 it appears they did not use the Kovalevsky protonation states
118 they sent us. *Vesper and de Groot (2013)* Thus we need more information to verify which
119 protonation states were used in the various simulations. Our comparison showed that the
120 protonation states of the histidine residues were very different, see Table 1. We note that
121 it is not sufficient to characterize the histidine residues as “protonated” or “deprotonated”.
122 Rather, it is also relevant whether protonation is at the δ or ϵ positions, for example His₁₄₃
123 which should be ϵ -protonated as it anchors the water network stabilizing His146 (see
124 Figure 6 in Ref. *El Hage et al. (2018)*).

125

126 Further differences between the simulations concern the shape of the simulation box
127 (cubic *El Hage et al. (2018)* vs. dodecahedral), the center of mass of the protein was
128 constrained to avoid periodic boundary effects *El Hage et al. (2018)*, and the terms for the
129 dihedral parameters for the Fe-proximal histidine differed. Removing the angular center
130 of mass motion is only warned against if the motion of the center of mass itself is not
131 controlled, i.e. if the solute can cross the boundaries of the periodic box. This, however, is
132 not the case in our simulations, but appeared to happen in some of theirs. Concerning
133 the effect of the box shape on the proteins simulated under PBC, it has been found that
134 the box type can have a statistically significant effect on the outcome of a simulation,
135 and that the magnitude of the effect depends on the protein considered. *Wassenaar and*
136 *Mark (2006)* Although all of the latter may contribute to the difference in the results, we
137 believe that a possible difference in the His protonation states used in the simulations
138 would play a major role and needs to be examined.

139

	Zheng et al. (Article)	Kovalevsky (De Groot)			Zheng et al. (Article)	Kovalevsky (De Groot)	
Res.	Chain A/C	Chain A	Chain C	Res.	Chain B/D	Chain B	Chain D
20	HSE	HSP	HSE	2	HSE	HSE	HSE
45	HSE	HSE	HSE	63	HSE	HSP	HSE
50	HSD	HSD	HSP	77	HSE	HSE	HSE
58	HSE	HSP	HSE	92	HSD - Fe	HSD - Fe	HSD - Fe
72	HSD	HSP	HSP	97	HSE	HSP	HSP
87	HSD-Fe	HSD -Fe	HSD-Fe	116	HSE	HSP	HSP
89	HSE	HSE	HSP	117	HSE	HSE	HSE
103	HSE	HSP	HSP	143	HSE	HSE	HSP
112	HSE	HSP	HSP	146	HSP	HSP	HSP
122	HSE	HSE	HSE				

Table 1. Histidine protonation states in Hb as used in the original work *El Hage et al. (2018)*; *Zheng et al. (2013)* and used in the files we obtained (Kovalevsky).

140 *Kinetics rather than thermodynamics:* A necessary but not sufficient criterion for thermo-
141 dynamic stability is that the structure considered (here T(0)) does not decay on the time
142 scale of the simulations (e.g. to R(0)). However, transition times from T to R can not be
143 determined from such an approach. For this, either a very large number of independent
144 simulations (on the order of hundreds to thousands, see below and Figure 2 above) are
145 required or free energy simulations need to be carried out. As pointed out in the original
146 article, *El Hage et al. (2018)* from the available experimental data the T(0) to R(0) transition
147 time should be on the order of seconds. The transitions in simulation boxes of 75 Å, 90 Å,
148 and 120 Å all were under one microsecond and increased with increasing box size, see
149 Figure 4. Panels (A), (B), and (D) show that the presence or absence of the Fe-His bond
150 does not lead to substantial changes of the time series as far as they have been followed.
151 Panel (B) also reports the changes for simulations with electrostatic cutoffs (green) and
152 when simulations with the Kovalevsky protonation states were carried out (orange). With
153 finite cutoff the T(0) state is stable for at least 150 ns whereas with the Kovalevsky pro-
154 tonation the T(0) state decays after 60 ns, in accord with earlier findings. *Hub et al. (2010)*

155
156 Comparisons of simulations with and without a Fe-His bond show that the Fe-His bond
157 lengths are comparable in all four subunits (see Figure 5). As to the Fe-Fe distances
158 between the various heme groups, only the 120 Å and 150 Å box simulations gave results
159 in agreement with experiment; the smaller boxes did not.

160
161 The 150 Å box in a T(0) state was stable for at least 1.3 microseconds, the length of the
162 simulation (Figure 1).

163
164 An obvious improvement of our initial study is to run multiple simulations for each box,
165 in particular if one is interested in the kinetics of the T-to-R transition. We are doing
166 additional simulations to examine the box size dependence of the lifetime. However, we
167 point out that it is very difficult to do a sufficient number of independent simulations to
168 obtain converged statistical results for a system the size of hemoglobin. In ten simulations

Figure 4. Temporal change of the C_{α} - C_{α} distance between His₁₄₆B1 and His₁₄₆B2 for the 75 Å box (A), 90 Å box (B), 120 Å box (C), and 150 Å box (D). In (A), (C), and (D) the black line reports the time series published and the red line shows the new time series obtained with the new simulation with the Fe-N bond. In (B) the black trace is from Ref. *El Hage et al. (2018)*, the red trace for the bonded Fe-His simulations, the green line from using finite cutoffs for evaluating the electrostatics (cutoff 14 Å), and the orange line from using Kovalevsky protonation states for all histidines. The black trace in panel B is reproduced from Figure 1 of El Hage et al 2018, eLife, published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

169 for the 120 Å box, the results reported to us were that 4 out of the 10 lasted longer than
 170 1 μ s, compared with 3 out of 10 for the 90 Å box. In simulation of kinetics hundreds to
 171 thousands of individual, reactive trajectories are required for converged reaction time
 172 distributions that can be compared with experiment. *Yosa and Meuwly (2011)*; *Soloviov*
 173 *et al. (2016)*

174

Figure 5. Fe-N_{His} bond lengths in simulations without (left) and with (right) explicit bond.

175 *Kinetics rather than thermodynamics:* The data in their Figure 3 cannot report on the
 176 kinetics because the number of events observed is too small, see Figure 2 in this Reply.

177

178 *Kinetics as a function of box size:* See Point-by-Point reply. We also note that the paper
 179 by Mark and Wassenaar *Wassenaar and Mark (2006)* did find a dependence on box shape.

180

181 *Thermodynamics as a function of box size:* The results for the other two systems are interest-
 182 ing but there is no reason to expect a box size dependence for the structural changes that
 183 were studied. Among other points, the surface area change is small and a hydrophobic
 184 effect is unlikely. There is no direct relationship to our findings for hemoglobin, as has
 185 also been noted by the Reviewers.

186

187 Conclusions

188 In contrast to the Conclusion of the Comment (See also the argument of G&G for not
 189 making changes in response to the review of their Comment and our Point-by-Point reply
 190 to their argument given below), we believe we have demonstrated that the details of
 191 our simulations provide evidence that there is a box size dependence in hemoglobin
 192 simulations and that is likely, though not proved, that in a 150 Å box the unliganded
 193 T state is stable. The role of the particular choice of His protonation states in the fast
 194 decay presented in the Comment remains to be evaluated. Finally, we reiterate that the
 195 unliganded T state is known to be stable from experiment so that if our results were not
 196 correct, there would have to be a yet unknown problem with simulations of unliganded T
 197 state hemoglobin.

198 Point-by-Point Reply

199 Point 1. In point 1, the reviewer focuses on the possibility that the box size effect on the
 200 conformational transition of large proteins cannot be excluded, although it is far from

Figure 6. Time-averaged radial distribution functions $g(r)$ between the C-terminal (COO) of His146 and water H for box sizes 90 Å (top) and 150 Å (middle) data from Figure 6 of Ref. *El Hage et al. (2018)* and from before and after the transition, obtained when using the Kovalevsky protonation in the 90 Å box. (bottom). Top and middle panel reproduced from Figure 6 of El Hage et al 2018, eLife, published under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License (CC BY 4.0; <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

201 established by the work of El Hage (2018). The Comment reports more repeats of simula-
 202 tions (approximately 10), than El Hage (just one), but it also falls short of establishing the
 203 statistical significance of an opposite observation for which hundreds or more simulations
 204 would be required. We have provided concrete data for a much smaller system in Figure

205 2 in our Reply.

206

207 "The reviewers believe it is important for both parties to not overstate the case, and to
208 clearly acknowledge that the box size effect remains a hypothesis, neither established
209 nor convincingly precluded. Unless the authors think this is not the case, the comment
210 should be revised to reflect this basic reality that neither parties in this debate knows the
211 ultimate answer here."

212

213 In response to this comment of the reviewers, Gapsys and de Groot (G&G in the
214 following) introduce a comment about the very low probability of longer lifetimes but
215 present no justification for this statement. Also, they quote a paper, which claims that only
216 10 repeats are required to obtain a statistically significant result. This contrasts sharply
217 with published papers *Yosa and Meuwly (2011)*; *Yosa Reyes et al. (2016)* (see also Figure 2
218 above) where thousands of events were found to be required to describe the kinetics. For
219 a comparison, see Figure 2 in Ref. *Miller and Gerber (2006)* where 100 simulations were
220 not sufficient to converge the reaction probability.

221

222 Point 2. The reviewer states "The discussion on the distinction between thermal and
223 kinetic stability in the first paragraph of the results section is not needed and should be
224 removed. (The corresponding section in the reply by El Hage et al. should be also be
225 removed.)"

226

227 Here we agree with G&G that the question of whether a kinetic or thermodynamic
228 effect is involved is important and should be discussed. However, this should only be
229 addressed once the simulation conditions have been established that lead to a thermody-
230 namically stable T(0) state, consistent with experiment. Moreover, we disagree with the
231 rationale of G&G for doing so. The purpose of El Hage et al. (2018) was never to quantify
232 the actual kinetics (i.e. transition time). In fact, it is explicitly stated and acknowledged
233 in El Hage et al. (2018) that "...the R(0) to T(0) transition time is about 20 μ s, much longer
234 than the simulation time."

235

236 The original study *El Hage et al. (2018)* reported on a possible simulation box size
237 effect on the T(0) stability and was motivated, as mentioned at the beginning of this
238 reply, by several published simulations of the T(0) state of hemoglobin, of which Hub et al.
239 (2010) was one. *Hub et al. (2010)* As stated in the Introduction of El Hage et al. (2018), it is
240 known from experiment that T(0) is stable so that the observation in the simulations of
241 Hub et al. (2010) that the T(0) state goes over to an R(0)-like state indicates that there is
242 something wrong with the thermodynamics. Further, that the T(0) to R(0) transition takes
243 place on the hundred nanosecond time scale, while it is known from experiment (see El
244 Hage et al., 2018) that such rare transitions require seconds, indicates that something
245 is also wrong with the kinetics in the simulations of G&G. Surprisingly, G&G still do not
246 seem to be aware of this fundamental problem with their simulations, independent of
247 our conclusion that special large boxes are required to stabilize the T(0) state. As we state
248 in the Conclusion to our Reply to the Comment:

249

250 "if our results were not correct, there would have to be a yet unknown problem with

251 the simulations of unliganded T state hemoglobin."

252

253 Point 3. The reviewer begins with the statement "It is known though rarely formally
254 acknowledged, that when the simulation length is far shorter than the actual time scale
255 of a molecular event, the simulation results are sensitive to the exact simulation set up.
256 We note that the setup of El Hage and by Gapsys and de Groot are not identical and the
257 differences in the setup potentially involve several parameters."

258

259 The reviewer then lists several differences between the simulation setups.

260

261 In their response, G&G point out that for the 90 Å box simulated with Gromacs we had
262 sent them our input files (as we believed we were still collaborating), and so it is likely that
263 the simulation conditions were identical. However, for the 120 Å and 150 Å boxes they
264 did not have our input files and so they generated the larger boxes in a rather arbitrary
265 manner by "adding a water layer (with solvated ions of 30 Angstroms and 60 Angstroms,
266 respectively." There is no reason to presume that this way of creating the larger boxes
267 yielded a setup that is identical to the ones we used. Given the coupling between the
268 protein conformation and water (pointed out on page 4 of the Reply to the Comment
269 and elaborated under point 4), it is very likely that the setups were, in fact, significantly
270 different.

271

272 We note here that also in the Simulation Section of the Comment, G&G list a set of
273 differences between our simulations and theirs that could be important since the effect
274 is subtle. Reviewer (1) suggests further communication to resolve the difference. G&G
275 declined to do so.

276

277 As to specific points of the reviewer where G&G are asked to revise their manuscript,
278 point (a) is essentially that discussed above and G&G only perpetuate their early neglect
279 of the likely difference in the setup of the larger boxes. On point (b) the response of G&G
280 is appropriate.

281

282 Point (c) refers to the protonation states used in the simulations. We point out in our
283 Reply that in Vesper and de Groot (2013) "it appears they did not use the Kovalevsky pro-
284 tonation states they sent us." Further, we state "Thus we need more information to verify
285 which protonation states were used in the various simulations." G&G sidestepped this
286 question and it remains unresolved at present, making their simulations less meaningful.

287

288 Point 4. This comment refers to the hydrophobic effect and the reviewers "suggest that
289 in the revision the authors make clear that the hydrophobic effect hypothesis is not
290 precluded although the original analysis by El Hage can be improved." G&G argue that the
291 various effects observed by El Hage, which suggested that there is a box size dependence,
292 can be explained as a simple dilution effect. However, as stated in our Reply, "we do not
293 agree with the constructs used in the Comment to reanalyze our results. These include:

294

295 "The subvolume analysis which attempts to compare the diffusivity in large boxes but
296 restricted to a smaller subvolume needs to introduce 'imaginary boundary conditions' and

297 it is unclear how this was done. Such an approach also appears to assume that water out-
 298 side this artificial volume behaves as bulk water. Alternatively, very short analysis times
 299 (2 ps) need to be used to avoid significant displacement of the water molecules.*Persson*
 300 *et al. (2017)*

301

302 The water-water hydrogen bond network reconfigures when the structure of the
 303 protein changes (T vs. R) and from one box size to another box size, see Figure 3 in
 304 Ref.*El Hage et al. (2018)*. Following a transition in the protein structure these changes
 305 occur on the few nanosecond time scale, as a direct response to the protein structure
 306 change. This suggests that the protein and water dynamics are coupled and can not be
 307 viewed independently."

308

309 This second point is an essential element that was neglected in the constructs of G&G
 310 and makes clear that the observed behavior cannot be ascribed to a simple dilution effect.

311

312 G&G responded: "...box size effect on the hydrophobic effect (as quantified by hydro-
 313 gen bonding, solvent RDF..) disappears when normalized.." basically says - or at least
 314 implies - that D. Chandler's analysis in Nature (2005)*Chandler (2005)* is incorrect as this
 315 work links the hydrophobic effect to the behaviour of the RDF and our analysis for the
 316 different box sizes reflect exactly that behaviour of the RDF. So something with the "nor-
 317 malization" in G&G must be wrong.

318

319 Point 5. The reviewer points out that "The authors' simulations of small proteins without
 320 observing a box size effect does not serve as proof to preclude the box size effect,
 321 especially for large systems. The authors should make this important caveat clear in their
 322 discussion." In fact, reviewer 2 in his reply to us states "..it seems unnecessary to report
 323 these simulations in the Comment. Or at least..are not conclusive either way." G&G state
 324 that they limit their findings to "for the investigated systems". Thus, they do mention
 325 the limitation, but the emphasis of what they wrote and what the reviewer requests are
 326 different.

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 330 by the CHARMM Development Project.

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